

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH AND MODELLING OF CFRP LAMINATES CREEP

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SUMMARY: Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) offer high specific mechanical properties (performance vs. weight ratio). Thus during the last decade, they have been increasingly used as components in engineering structures and particularly for aeronautical applications. However, this type of complex material with organic matrix shows, even at the room temperature, mechanical characteristics depending strongly on the duration of loading and/or the stress or strain rate. This behaviour is obviously amplified by an increase of temperature or by a particular environment as the occurrence of moisture or low-molecular weight plasticizing agent (jet fuels, lubricants or other hydrocarbons). So, concerning the design of such structural components, one of the most important feature of the long-term durability and dimensional stability is to take account of their long-term viscoelastic behaviour. To foresee the long-term integrity of a composite structure, the viscoelastic behaviour of the polymeric part of these materials have to be understood.

In this contribution a long-term prediction method for creep behaviour of off-axis CFRP (unidirectional 90° and $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates) is proposed using both the classical time-temperature-stress superposition principle (TTSSP) and a new microscopic approach based on a theory of the non elastic deformation of amorphous polymers developed from a model of molecular mobility.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, Flexural Creep, Long-term behavior, TTSSP, Molecular mobility, Amorphous polymer

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) offer high specific mechanical properties (performance vs. weight ratio). Thus during the last decade, they have been increasingly used as components in engineering structures and particularly for aeronautical applications. However, most forms of CFRP subjected to steady long-term loading exhibit time-dependant behaviour (creep) even from ambient temperature. The magnitude of creep strain (deformation, behaviour) was enhanced by temperature, humidity and load level and depended very much upon stacking sequence. As carbon fibres generally used for the reinforcement of polymers exhibit negligible time-dependent behaviour, creep is very low in unidirectional composites loaded in the longitudinal direction. Any angle-ply composites or unidirectional

fibre composites subjected to transverse loading, exhibit time-dependant behaviour since it is dominated by the matrix viscoelastic properties.

This work deals with a procedure based on a new microscopic approach based on a theory of the non elastic deformation of amorphous polymers developed from a model of molecular mobility for predicting the long-term behaviour of statically loaded UD 90° and [±45°] laminates from short-term tests. The results were compared to the classical time-temperature-stress superposition principle (TTSSP).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The materials used are UD 90° and [±45°] carbon fibre (HTA200)/epoxy(M18/1) laminates (24 plies) produced by compression moulding process (cured 24 min. at 80°C then 2h at 125°C and post-cured 3h at 190°C). The fibre volume fraction V_f is about 60%. The crosslinking rate is 94 % ±2 and the mechanical glass transition temperature of the matrix determined by DSC is 210°C. Moreover, M18/1 resin specimen were processed.

Techniques and tests

CFRP and resin samples were subjected to three-point bending monotonic and creep tests. The samples were about 100 mm long, 25 mm width, 3.5 mm thick. The span to depth was equal to 30. Three test temperatures were chosen using internal friction results measured at low frequency (0,01 Hz) by torsion dynamic spectrometry versus temperature on the neat resin: 23° and 90°C very below the mechanical α relaxation associated to the glass transition and 150°C at the beginning of the internal friction increase link to the first large-scale molecular motions (Figure 1a).

Figure 1 : Neat resin : (a) : G' and $\tan\delta$ as a function of temperature ; (b) Cole-Cole diagram

Monotonic tests

The monotonic bending tests were performed with a constant cross-head speed of 2 mm/min and allow the determination of the ultimate stress in order to determine the load levels for the creep tests. The unidirectional composites transversely loaded showed a linear behaviour up to failure whatever the test temperature. The specimen failed suddenly perpendicular to the loading direction. Figure 2 indicated that failure is typical of strongly bonded composite. The process of failure involves mainly cohesive failure phenomena in the interfibre zone by both transverse tension and shear of the matrix [1]. This is pointed out in Figure 2 by the presence of "cups" characteristic of this type of damage. The matrix is confined by the fibres and can not deform, leading to low elongation to failure compared with neat resin one (Table 1). It explains the low dependence with the temperature of the ultimate properties.

Figure 2 : Post mortem scanning electron micrograph of a failure feature observed on UD90°

For the angle-ply composites the stress-strain curve is non-linear since the behaviour is dominated by shear matrix properties and can reach larger strain values compared with the unidirectional laminates. The non-linear behaviour observed on stress-strain curve can be attributed first to non-linear viscoelastic and viscoplastic shear behaviour of the resin and interface and then to the occurrence of damage although it is difficult to separate these two processes. Indeed, for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates, because the maximum shear stress operated at 45° to the loading axis, high intralaminar shear occurred close or at fibre matrix interface in each individual ply and was associated to fibre rotation that tend to lie closer to the load axis. It results matrix transverse failures and delamination because adjacent plies move in opposite directions and extensive shear take place between neighbouring plies [2]. The transition from linear into marked non linear behaviour and the maximum stress decrease with temperature, because the ductility increase too. No global failure occurred whatever the temperature.

Table 1 provides the values of strength (σ_p) and elongation (ϵ_p) at failure for the unidirectional composites and the maximum stress (σ_m) and associated strain (ϵ_m) for the $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates.

T (°C)	Stress (MPa)			Strain (%)			Flexural Modulus		
	at failure, σ_r		max, σ_m	at failure, ϵ_r		max, ϵ_m	E _{app.} (GPa)		
	Matrix	UD 90°	±45°	Matrix	UD 90°	±45°	Matrix	UD 90°	±45°
23	88 (2%)	88 (6%)	345 (2%)	2,9 (2%)	1,05 (4%)	4,95 (2%)	3,3 (2%)	8,5 (6%)	15 (3%)
90	-	72 (6%)	320 (14%)	-	0,95 (4%)	3,4 (8%)	-	8 (2%)	15 (10%)
150	-	77 (2%)	255 (8%)		1 (5%)	3,1 (8%)	-	8 (2%)	14 (18%)

Table 1: Mean monotonic mechanical properties (coefficients of variation in the parentheses)

Creep tests

The creep tests were realised at different load levels (in the 50-85% of the expected ultimate flexural strength range at room temperature) until two months or sample failure.

Figures 3a and 3b show flexural creep strain (that is the strain which takes place with time when the material is under constant load, following the initial "instantaneous" elastic rapid deformation) at 150°C for unidirectional composite subjected to transverse load and angle-ply laminates [±45°] respectively.

Figure 3 : Creep strain as a function of time for UD90° (a) and [±45°] laminates (b) at T=150°.

The curves showed marked dependence on stress. For UD composites, creep can be subdivided into two categories : the primary creep indicating a transition state and the secondary or steady state creep occurring at constant stress. The tertiary creep, characterised by a rapid increase of the inelastic strain did not appear and even for the lowest stress levels the steady state region was quite narrow. On the contrary, the tertiary creep region dominated the creep behaviour at 150°C when the stress was high enough in the case of [±45°] laminates.

Moreover, the isochronal stress-strain curves plotted from creep data showed a non-linear behaviour even from room temperature i.e. the creep compliance depended upon the level of the applied stress. Obviously, this non-linearity was emphasised with both the level of the applied stress and the time under load. This non-linear behaviour was more pronounced for the [±45°] laminates. This is due to the fact that in this case the interlaminar zone and intralaminar fibre-matrix interface (maximum shear direction) were subjected to very high shear stress and has to be connected with the appearance of tertiary creep at high temperature and applied stress level.

LONG-TERM BEHAVIOUR PREDICTION

In a first time, it is shown that the determination of time-temperature and time-stress shift factors and the plot of the creep compliance master curve using classic TTSS principle allows to estimate the long-term behaviour of the composites (UD 90° and [±45°]). Then, a new microscopic approach based on a theory of the non elastic deformation of amorphous polymers developed from a model of molecular mobility leads to equivalent result and can be used in FEM analysis.

Time Temperature Stress Superposition Principle (TTSSP)

This method is based on the fact that creep is accelerated by temperature and/or stress i.e. an increase in temperature and/or stress shift the creep spectra towards shorter time. If the compliance log-time curves determined at high temperature and/or stress level during short time are shifted to the lower temperature and/or stress level along the log-time axis by a suitable shift factor, the curves overlap to form a reduced compliance curve. This "master curve" represents the creep behaviour for a given thermomechanical condition (temperature and applied stress), extending over many decades of times.

This procedure has been used extensively in experimental studies [3] with reliable results. However, this method is usually invalid if structural changes, ageing for example, or damage occur in the material at higher temperature or stress level. In this work, the effect of possible physical ageing can be ignored because the test temperatures are below enough the glass temperature. The macroscopic damage is, in first approximation, considered as negligible.

The results from tests on the UD composite transversely loaded were used to construct a smooth master curve at a reference condition 23°C and 62 MPa by shifting first the creep data obtained at different applied stress levels horizontally to 62 MPa for each test temperature and then the reduced curves at 62 MPa to 23°C. As the failure occurred at 150°C for an anelastic strain of about $2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the master curve was not plotted above the compliance $J = 3,89 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ that is about a six-year period (Figure 5). Using the same procedure, a master curve for a ten-year period at a room temperature and stress level 172 MPa was developed from short time tests for the $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates (Figure 6). In this case, the tests performed at higher thermomechanical conditions for which extensive damage was observed (i.e. $\sigma > 0.65\sigma_m$ at $T = 90^\circ$ and $\sigma > 0.50\sigma_m$ at $T = 150^\circ$ with σ_m expected ultimate flexural strength at room temperature) will not considered to form the master curve.

For the two composites the time-stress shift factors was found to be a linear function of the stress independent of the test temperature. The time-temperature shift factors is quantitatively in good agreement with Arrhenius' equation.

Because the master curves are graphically produced this technique is difficult to automate. Schapery has developed [4] a modelling of time-dependent behaviour based on thermodynamic constitutive theory which is in fact the analytical expression of the TTSSP, if the material shows a non-linear behaviour. However, the use of Schapery method required both creep and creep recovery data.

Microscopic approach

Definition

This approach [5-9] assumed that the macroscopic deformation mechanism was linked to the nucleation and growth of shear microdomains (smd). The primary motions associated to sub-T_g or β relaxation occurred under the effect of applied stress in regions where the molecular density is smaller than the average one (defects) and then the resistance to shear is lower than in the rest of the sample. It induced hierarchically correlated molecular motions resulting in nucleation of such domains. Following the duration loading as compared as a characteristic time related to the relaxation time of the β -relaxation, t_β , the strain was recovered or plastic deformation took place when the stress was removed. According

to these assumptions, Perez et al. showed that the anelastic behaviour of an amorphous polymer can be expressed by the following relationship giving the anelastic compliance, J_{an} versus time :

$$J_{an}(t) = A_n \left(1 - \exp - \left(\frac{t}{\tau_m} \right)^k \right) + A_{vp} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_m} \right)^h \quad (1)$$

where : A_n is the maximal anelastic strain for a given thermomechanical condition,

h and k are parameters connected to the effects of correlation for the molecular motion in the amorphous polymer matrix,

$A_{vp} = A_n h^{-1} k^{h/k}$, a parameter linked to the viscoplastic strain rate,

and τ_m is a characteristic time given by the following relationship : $\tau_m = (\tau_\beta k t_0^{k-1})^{1/k}$, where t_0 is a scaling time parameter linked to the gap (in frequency and temperature) between the β -relation and α -relaxation and τ_β is the relaxation time of the β -relaxation. The energy barrier which have to be jumped during β motions are overcome by thermal fluctuation, but the application of a stress can introduce β -motions through mechanical process. Thus the β -relaxation time can be expressed as followed in the case of a parabolic shaped energy barrier [9] :

$$\tau_\beta = \tau_{0\beta} \exp \left(\frac{U_\beta}{kT} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^{3/2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where U_β is the apparent activation energy associated to β -process, σ the applied stress and σ_0 the stress required to jump the energy barrier when no thermal energy is available i.e. at 0°K. is about (order of magnitude of) $G_0/2\pi$ where is the shear modulus at 0°K. The expression (3) shows the effect of the stress level on the apparent activation energy ($\Delta H_a = U_\beta (1 - \sigma/\sigma_0)^{3/2}$) when the material is subjected to large stress and takes into account the non linear mechanical behaviour.

The first part of expression (1) is linked to the recoverable anelastic strain i.e. the nucleation and reversible growth of the smd and the second part to the viscoplastic behaviour.

Estimation of parameters ; case of transversely loaded unidirectional laminates

The different parameters required to use the modelling are experimentally available using dynamic mechanical spectrometry. U_β and $t_{0\beta}$ are determined using loss factor as a function of temperature spectra at different frequencies in the β -process temperature range (Figure 1a). The parameters h and k can be obtained from G'' against G' complex plane plot, so-called "Cole-Cole diagram" (Figure 1b). In fact, the Fourier transform of the relation (1) is similar to the well-known rheological expression corresponding to the limited bi-parabolic modelling [10], but in equation (1) all the parameters have a physical meaning. The slope of tangents at the ends of the Cole-Cole plot in the α -region led to h ($\omega \rightarrow 0$) and k ($\omega \rightarrow \infty$). G_0 is given by extrapolation of this diagram to $G''=0$ in the highest G' β -region and t_0 is obtained assuming that the matrix viscosity at glass temperature, T_g is about 10^{12} Pas [7]. All these values are summarised in Table 2. Figure 4a showed the anelastic compliance plotted logarithmically

versus time in the case of the neat matrix at room temperature and the 90° UD composite at 23°, 90°C and 150°C and for two maximal stress levels. The creep behaviour of both resin and composite is well described by a linear regression through the log J, log t values except at the very beginning probably due to loading difficulties. The slope of the creep curve plotted in log log scale is about of 0.28 that is of the same order of magnitude that the parameter k determined by dynamic mechanical spectrometry, even if this latest value is relatively difficult to obtain due to the β -relaxation process occurrence. By neglecting, in a first approximation, the viscoplastic behaviour (i.e. for short time and low stress level) the expression (1) is simplified to :

$$J_{an}(t) \approx A_n \left(\frac{t}{\tau_m} \right)^k \quad (3)$$

This function is represented in log-log scale (Log J_{an} , log t) by a straight line with k as slope. It may be seen that the creep behaviour is well linked to correlation effect. This slope and therefore creep rate depended directly on hierarchical correlation effects which govern the molecular motions and the growth of shear microdomains. Thus the increase of these correlation effects reduce the creep sensibility by k decrease. It appears that this global behaviour is mainly in relation with the mechanical properties of the matrix and of the interfacial zone and can be described thanks to a parameter connected to the effects of correlation for the molecular motion in the amorphous polymer matrix.

The stress and strain state of the matrix in the composite is complex due to the presence of fibres, eventually voids. Moreover, the stress and strain distribution in the case of 3-point bending test is non-uniform. In order to take into account this complexity, A_n was taken as an adjustable parameter. The identification of A_n was made using experimental creep results at one week (in order to ensure to be beyond the loading zone and in viscoelastic domain).

Case of ± 45 laminates

The same approach was led on angle-ply laminates. As for UD, the creep compliance curves plotted in double-logarithmic co-ordinates can be described by a set of straight lines of slope 0.28 (at least partially for the higher level temperature) except for higher temperature and stress level test conditions where a fast increase of the compliance occurred (Figure 4b). This phenomenon is linked to the occurrence of extensive intra-ply transverse failures and delamination, as previously mentioned. As for the TSSTP, only the thermomechanical conditions with no macroscopic damage were considered.

Figure 4 : Flexural creep compliance as a function of time in log log scale

Long-term behaviour

As an example, the creep compliance was determined for the same thermomechanical condition than the master curves i.e. 23°C and 62 MPa for the unidirectional composites (until six years), and 23°C and 172 MPa in the case of the angle-ply laminates (until 10 years). The comparison between the two methods was given Figure 5 and Figure 6 for the UD 90 and [+45] laminates respectively. The Figure 5 shows that the long-term creep compliance determined from microstructural approach is in the error range of the master curve for the UD 90°. For the [+45°] laminates a divergence between the two approach occurred at about 10⁶ minutes. The microscopic approach overestimated the viscoplastic behaviour. This result can be in part explain by the fact that the fibres tend to rotate and then lie closer to the tensile axis when the composite is subjected to tensile load. As a consequence, the viscoelastic deformation is probably prevent to occur. Nevertheless, this technique appeared as a promising way in order to extrapolate long-term creep behaviour using dynamic mechanical spectrometry results and creep shorter tests (1 week) performed at the wished temperature.

	k	h	U_{β} (ev)	$\tau_{o\beta}$ (s)	σ/σ_0	t_0 (s)	A_n (MPa ⁻¹)
UD 90°	0.28	0.4	0.48	$1.09 \cdot 10^{-12}$	0.114	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
[±45°]	0.28	0.4	0.48	$1.09 \cdot 10^{-12}$	0.37	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Table 2 : Parameters of the Perez modelling

Figure 5 : UD 90° : Comparison of the two approaches

Figure 6 : [±45°] laminates : Comparison of the two approaches

CONCLUSION

It appears that this global behaviour is mainly in relation with the mechanical properties of the matrix and of the interfacial zone and can be described thanks to a parameter connected to the effects of correlation

for the molecular motion in the amorphous polymer matrix. In this case, the anelastic compliance is given as analytic expression and can be integrated in FEM codes. It is an important result because it connects the physics of the polymer to the long-term behaviour of the material. A more accurate study is nevertheless necessary in order to precise the influence of the presence of fibres on the microstructure of the polymer, but it is a promising way. Moreover, the global interpretation of the results obtained on the $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminate requires two complementary approaches: the microscopic approach describing the viscoelastic and viscoplastic behaviour of the matrix for the tests at weakest stress levels and a mesoscopic approach describing the damage.

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